

Effectiveness of planned health teaching on knowledge regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy at selected hospitals of city.

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: The Purpose of the study was The most frequently given medications for controlling blood coagulation in patients with AF, rheumatic valvular illness, heart valve replacement (HVR), Deep vein thrombosis (DVT), pulmonary embolism, and following orthopedic surgery are vitamin K antagonists like warfarin, Acenocoumarol, etc. In the US, warfarin is a highly common medication prescribed, however in India, acenocoumarol is the preferred medication. The most frequent cause of death is venous thromboembolism, which affects roughly 3% of people with deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and 15% of those with pulmonary embolism. Statistics from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) show that 10 to 30 percent of patients pass away within a month of being diagnosed. The most significant side effect of oral anticoagulation (OAC) with vitamin K antagonists is bleeding. While bleeding is inescapably associated with OAC, it may significantly affect the prognosis of treated subjects by resulting in treatment termination, lifelong impairment, or death. The annual incidence of significant bleeding, fatal hemorrhage, and cerebral bleeding during OAC is 2%–5%, 0.5%–1%, and 0.2%–0.4%, respectively. In general practice, oral anticoagulation therapy (OAT) presents a problem, particularly for high-risk populations like the elderly. One of the main causes of difficulties is thought to be a lack of patient education regarding OAT safety-relevant issues

METHOD: The research methodology adopted for the study was quantitative research approach. The investigator used Quasi experimental, non-randomized, one group pretest posttest design. The study was based on the Imogene King's Goal Attainment theory. Accessible population for this study consisted, patients receiving anticoagulant therapy at selected hospitals of city and who are available during the study. The setting for the study was selected hospitals of city. Sample size was 53. Patients receiving anticoagulant therapy, were selected with the help of non-probability convenient sampling technique. Patients were selected as per the inclusion criteria from the selected hospitals of city. Tool consists of demographic data, structured questionnaire for knowledge assessment. The data was collected on from 14/11/2022– 15/12/2022 .Before Data Collection the consent was taken from the participants. Pre-test knowledge of was assessed participants, and planned health teaching was provided to them. Document

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help of non-probability convenient sampling technique. Patients were selected as per the inclusion criteria from the selected hospitals of city. Tool consists of demographic data, structured questionnaire for knowledge assessment. The data was collected on from 14/11/2022– 15/12/2022 .Before Data Collection the consent was taken from the participants. Pre-test knowledge of was assessed participants, and planned health teaching was provided to them. Documented the post intervention knowledge on 7th day ted the post intervention knowledge on 7th day.

RESULT: 11.3% of the patients receiving anticoagulant therapy had age above 18-20 years, 28.3% of them had age 21-30 years, 15.1% of them had age 31-40 years, and 18.9% of them had age 41-50 years and 26.4% of them had age above 51 years. 60.4% of them were males and 39.6% of them were females. In pretest, 69.8% of the patients receiving anticoagulant therapy had poor knowledge (score 0-6) and 30.2% of them had average knowledge (score 7-13) regarding anticoagulant therapy. Average knowledge score in pretest was 5.3 which increased to 9.8 in posttest. T-value for this test was 11.1 with 52 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average knowledge score in posttest was significantly higher than that in pretest. None of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the knowledge.

CONCLUSION:

With the above findings it is clear that the planned health teaching helped to improve knowledge in patients receiving anticoagulant therapy. Analysis of data shows that there was significant difference in knowledge score in pretest and posttest score.

(Key words :Patients receiving anticoagulant therapy, anticoagulant therapy, Knowledge, planned health teaching.)

INTRODUCTION: Vitamin K antagonists like warfarin, Acenocoumarol, etc., are the most frequently prescribed drugs for managing blood coagulation in patients with AF, rheumatic valvular disease, heart valve replacement (HVR), Deep vein thrombosis (DVT), pulmonary embolism, and after orthopaedic surgery. Warfarin is very popularly prescribed in the US whereas in India Acenocoumarol is the drug of choice. A report suggests that in North India Acenocoumarol is widely used in place of warfarin. Recently, with the advent of new oral anticoagulation's many questions have risen as to will the new agents replace the older oral anticoagulation's and are they much more effective than the older oral anticoagulation's. The use of newer agents in India is reduced due to higher cost, poor compliance, minimal monitoring facilities, no specific antidote available, and serious bleeding in renal impaired patients and elderly > 80 years Venous thromboembolism (VTE) and atrial fibrillation (AF) implicate a high burden of mortality and morbidity. In India, VTE events occur annually and 53.6% of the hospitalized Indian patients are at an increased risk of VTE. The age group commonly affected with VTE is 41–60 years. Warfarin, the conventional oral anticoagulant has several limitations and challenges, such as resistance due to Vitamin K epoxide Reductase Complex 1 (VKORC1) genetic polymorphisms, a narrow therapeutic window with international normalized ratio (INR) range 2–3, routine coagulation monitoring, unpredictable pharmacokinetics, slow-onset/offset of action, increased risk of bleeding including intracranial haemorrhage, dose adjustment, dietary restrictions, drug interactions, high coefficient of inter-lab variation in INR estimation; INR is not reflective of monthly or long-term control When compared to the western community, Indians consume a different diet. Inconsistent consumption of green leafy vegetables such as cabbage, cauliflower, spinach, and other foods rich in vitamin K in the Indian diet would prevent patients with Vitamin K antagonist (VKA) from achieving the target international normalised ratio (INR) and cause problems with INR values. Over-the-counter (OTC) drugs (NSAIDs, alternative herbal products such as garlic and fenugreek) increase the

Oral anticoagulant (OAC) action of the Vitamin K antagonist (VKA) and may cause haemorrhage. In India, certain antipyretics such as paracetamol (PCM) and antituberculous drugs can cause over or under coagulation Monitoring is a major issue because Indian hospitals lack laboratories that measure prothrombin time (PT)/INR in a standardised manner. Several Indian studies have found that outpatient anticoagulant control was generally poor, with inadequate pretherapeutic assessment, an unacceptable proportion of subtherapeutic PT/INR values, and high complication rates; an inadequate clinician knowledge base for oral anticoagulant targets; and irregular PT monitoring in 25% of patients. 1-3 recent pharmacogenetics findings show that genetic factors influence the clinical outcomes of oral anticoagulant therapy.

METHOD:

Study Design: Quasi-experimental, one group pretest posttest design.

Setting: Selected hospitals of city.

Sampling Technique : non-probability sampling techniques.

Population: Above 18 years of age

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION FOR MAIN STUDY

Approval from the research committee members & authorities is obtained to conduct research.

- a. The purpose of the research is explained to the samples.
- b. Informed consent is obtained from samples.
- c. Assessed the knowledge among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy at 50 selected hospitals of city.
- d. The planned health teaching is provided to samples.
- e. Assessed the post intervention knowledge of samples on 7th days of intervention

The data gathering process began from 14/11/2022– 15/12/2022. A formal permission was obtained from concerned authority. Subjects were taken from the selected areas using nonprobability convenient sampling technique. The investigator introduced self and informed the samples about the nature of the study So as to ensure better co-operation during the data collection. Objectives of study were discussed and the confidentiality of the data. Each subject was given prepared tool containing section A (socio demographic questionnaire) and Section B (structured questionnaire).

PLAN FOR STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The purpose of analysis is to minimize or arrange the data and give it significance.⁷⁰

The systematical organizing and synthesis of research data, as well as the testing of research hypotheses utilizing those data, is known as analysis. In the master sheet, the data is plotted.

Demographic data consist of 10 items analyzed by frequency distribution, percentage, table and relevant graphs.

A structured questionnaire was used to assess of knowledge regarding regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy. The collected data was coded,

tabulated, and analyzed by using descriptive statistics (mean, percentage, standard deviation). The researcher planned to analyze the data in the following manner.

Section I

This section deals with the data pertaining to the demographic variables of the patients receiving anticoagulant therapy includes Age, Gender, Educational 51 status, Occupation ,Disease suffering from ,Duration of disorder ,Duration of anticoagulation consumption, Information on anticoagulation received, Regular investigations carried out as advised by the physician, Regular treatment taken as advised by the physician .

Frequency and percentages distribution used to describe demographic variables and presented in the forms of table and graphs.

Section II:

Analysis of data related to knowledge before providing planned health teaching regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy at selected hospitals of city.

Section III:

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of planned health teaching on knowledge regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy at selected hospitals of city

Section IV:

Analysis of data related to association of pre intervention study findings with selected demographic variables.

Section I

Description of samples (patients receiving anticoagulant therapy) based on their personal characteristics

Table 1: Description of samples (patients receiving anticoagulant therapy) based on their personal characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage

N=60

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Age		
18-20 years	6	11.3%
21-30 years	15	28.3%
31-40 years	8	15.1%
41-50 years	10	18.9%
51 years and above	14	26.4%
Gender		
Male	32	60.4%
Female	21	39.6%
Occupation		
Private employee	14	26.4%
Business	5	9.4%
House wife	16	30.2%
Daily wagers	18	34.0%
Education		
Primary	14	26.4%
Secondary	24	45.3%
Higher secondary	10	18.9%
Under graduate	5	9.4%
Disease suffering from		
Angina	7	13.2%
Arrhythmias	1	1.9%
Heart valve disease	10	18.9%
Congestive cardiac failure	5	9.4%
Aortic stenosis	3	5.7%
Cardiomyopathy	3	5.7%
Myocardial infraction	13	24.5%
Cerebrovascular accident	11	20.8%

Table 1 cont....

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Duration of disorder		
Less than 1 year	40	75.5%
1 to 4 years	5	9.4%
More than 4 years	8	15.1%
Duration of anticoagulation consummation		
Less than 1 year	40	75.5%
1 to 4 years	5	9.4%
More than 4 years	8	15.1%
Education on anticoagulation received		
No	53	100.0%
Regular investigation carried out as advised by physician		
Yes	53	100.0%
Regular treatment taken as advised by physician		
Yes	53	100.0%

9.4% of the patients receiving anticoagulant therapy had age 18-20 years, 28.3% of them had age 21-30 years, 15.1% of them had age 31-40 years, 18.9% of them had age 41-50 years and 26.4% of them had age above 50 years. 60.4% of them were males and 39.6% of them were females.

26.4% if them were private employees, 9.4% of them had business, 30.2% of them were housewives and 34% of them were daily wagers.

26.4% of them had primary education, 45.3% of them had secondary education, 18.9% of them had higher secondary education and 9.4% of them were under graduates.

13.2% of them were suffering from angina, 1.9% of them had Arrhythmias, 18.9% of them had heart valve disease, 9.4% of them had congestive cardia failure, 5.7% of them had aortic stenosis, 5.7% of them had cardiomyopathy, 24.5% of them had myocardial infraction and 20.8% of them had cerebrovascular accident.

75.5% of them had disorder for less than one year, 9.4% of them had disorder for 1 to 4 years and 15.1% of them had disorder for more than 4 years.

75.5% of them were consuming anticoagulation for less than one year, 9.4% of them were consuming anticoagulation for 1 to 4 years and 15.1% of them were consuming anticoagulation.

None of them had received education on anticoagulation.

All of them had carried regular investigation as advised by physician.

All of them had taken regular treatment as advised by physician.

Section I

Description of samples (patients receiving anticoagulant therapy) based on their personal characteristics

**Table 4.1: Distribution of demographic data of samples in group
according to their age of the patients**

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Age		
18-20 years	6	11.30%
21-30 years	15	28.30%
31-40 years	8	15.10%
41-50 years	10	18.90%
51 years and above	14	26.40%

11.3% of the patients receiving anticoagulant therapy had age 18-20 years, 28.3% of them had age 21-30 years, 15.1% of them had age 31-40 years, and 18.9% of them had age 41-50 years and 26.4% of them had age above 51 years.

Figure 4.1: Pie diagram showing percentage wise distribution of patients according to the age

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Gender		
Male	32	60.40%
Female	21	39.60%

Figure 4.2: Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of patients according to their gender.

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Occupation		
Private employee	14	26.40%
Business	5	9.40%
Housewife	16	30.20%
Daily wagers	18	34.00%

Figure 4.3: Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of patients according to their occupation.

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Education		
Primary	14	26.40%
Secondary	24	45.30%
Higher secondary	10	18.90%
Undergraduate	5	9.40%

Figure 4.4: Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of patients according to their educational qualification.

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Disease suffering from		
Angina	7	13.20%
Arrhythmias	1	1.90%
Heart valve disease	10	18.90%
Congestive cardiac failure	5	9.40%
Aortic stenosis	3	5.70%
Cardiomyopathy	3	5.70%
Myocardial infraction	13	24.50%
Cerebrovascular accident	11	20.80%

Figure 4.5: Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of patients according to their disease suffering from.

Demographic Variable	Freq	%
Duration of disorder		
Less than 1 year	40	75.50%
1 to 4 years	5	9.40%
More than 4 years	8	15.10%

Figure 4.6: Pie diagram showing percentage wise distribution of patients according to their duration of disorder

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Duration of anticoagulation consumption		
Less than 1 year	40	75.50%
1 to 4 years	5	9.40%
More than 4 years	8	15.10%

75.5% of them were consuming anticoagulation for less than one year, 9.4% of them were consuming anticoagulation for 1 to 4 years and 15.1% of them were consuming anticoagulation.

Figure 4.7: Pie diagram showing percentage wise distribution of patients according to their duration of anticoagulation consumption

Section II

Analysis of data related to the level of knowledge before providing planned health teaching regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy

Table 2: Level of knowledge before providing planned health teaching regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy

Knowledge	Pretest	
	Freq	%
Poor (score 0-6)	37	69.8%
Average (score 7-13)	16	30.2%
Good (score 14-20)	0	0.0%

In pretest, 69.8% of the patients receiving anticoagulant therapy had poor knowledge (score 0-6) and 30.2% of them had average knowledge (score 7-13) regarding anticoagulant therapy.

Section III

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of planned health teaching on knowledge regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy at selected hospitals of city

Table 3: Effectiveness of planned health teaching on knowledge regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy at selected hospitals of city

N=60

Knowledge	Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Poor (score 0-6)	37	69.8%	6	11.3%
Average (score 7-13)	16	30.2%	42	79.2%
Good (score 14-20)	0	0.0%	5	9.4%

In pretest, 69.8% of the patients receiving anticoagulant therapy had poor knowledge (score 0-6) and 30.2% of them had average knowledge (score 7-13) regarding anticoagulant therapy. In posttest, 11.3% of the patients receiving anticoagulant therapy had poor knowledge (score 0-6), 79.2% of them had average knowledge (score 7-13) and 9.4% of them had good knowledge (score 14-20) regarding anticoagulant therapy. This indicates that the knowledge regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy improved remarkably after planned health teaching.

Table 4: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of planned health teaching on knowledge regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy at selected hospitals of city
N=60

	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>	<u>T</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>p-value</u>
Pretest	5.3	1.9	11.1	52	0.000
Posttest	9.8	2.4			

Researcher applied Paired t-test for the effectiveness of planned health teaching on knowledge regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy. Average knowledge score in pretest was 5.3 which increased to 9.8 in posttest. T-value for this test was 11.1 with 52 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average knowledge score in posttest was significantly higher than that in pretest. It is evident that the planned health teaching is significantly effective in improving the knowledge regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy.

Table 5: Item analysis

N=60

Knowledge item	Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
The common site for clot formation in body is	10	18.9%	30	56.6%
Following are examples of anticoagulants EXCEPT	18	34.0%	26	49.1%
The action of anticoagulant drug is to	16	30.2%	42	79.2%
The anticoagulant drug is advised for	11	20.8%	32	60.4%
Anticoagulant therapy is avoided in case of	22	41.5%	33	62.3%
Abnormal INR level can lead to	3	5.7%	16	30.2%
The most common side effect of anticoagulant therapy is	7	13.2%	25	47.2%
The common side effects of the drug other than bleeding	25	47.2%	15	28.3%
While taking anticoagulant drug, which of the following may lead to emergency consultation	4	7.5%	17	32.1%
The drinks should avoid during anticoagulant therapy is	14	26.4%	33	62.3%
The food that can affect the action of anticoagulant drug	7	13.2%	27	50.9%
The INR level should be checked at least once in	17	32.1%	23	43.4%
The international normalized ratio (INR) measures	26	49.1%	50	94.3%
If in case you are taking drug known to interact with anticoagulant therapy what will you do	15	28.3%	17	32.1%
The blood test to be done during anticoagulant therapy	25	47.2%	52	98.1%
If anticoagulant drug dose is missed, the required action to be taken is	5	9.4%	7	13.2%
The normal INR level is	18	34.0%	9	17.0%
The activity that should be avoided during the therapy is	6	11.3%	23	43.4%
Which of the following activities are more risky while taking anticoagulant drug	21	39.6%	22	41.5%
The best time of day for taking anticoagulant drug	9	17.0%	21	39.6%

Table 5 presents the frequency and percentage of correct responses by patients receiving anticoagulant therapy to each of the knowledge item. It is clear that the correct responses increased after planned health teaching.

Section IV**Analysis of data related to the association of knowledge with selected demographic variables****Table 6: Fisher's exact test for the association of knowledge with selected demographic****Variables****N=60**

Demographic variable		Knowledge		p-value
		Average	Poor	
Age	18-20 years	1	5	0.971
	21-30 years	5	10	
	31-40 years	3	5	
	41-50 years	3	7	
	51 years and above	4	10	
Gender	Male	9	23	0.764
	Female	7	14	
Occupation	Private employee	5	9	0.502
	Business	0	5	
	House wife	6	10	
	Daily wagers	5	13	
Education	Primary	3	11	0.823
	Secondary	8	16	
	Higher secondary	3	7	
	Under graduate	2	3	
Disease suffering from	Angina	1	6	0.855
	Arrhythmias	0	1	
	Heart valve disease	3	7	
	Congestive cardiac failure	2	3	
	Aortic stenosis	0	3	
	Cardiomyopathy	1	2	
	Myocardial infraction	4	9	
Duration of disorder	Less than 1 year	13	27	0.407
	1 to 4 years	0	5	
	More than 4 years	3	5	
Duration of anticoagulation consummation	Less than 1 year	13	27	0.407
	1 to 4 years	0	5	
	More than 4 years	3	5	

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the knowledge regarding anticoagulant therapy among patients receiving anticoagulant therapy.

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